

Table 1. Mean effect of tillage, weed control practice, and N level on performance of rice and dry weight of weeds at harvest. Cuttack, India.

Treatment	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Panicle weight (g)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Weed dry weight (g m ⁻²)
Tillage						
Summer plowing	115	67	2.79	2.78	3.12	67
Conventional tillage	116	58	2.57	1.98	2.86	142
SE	1.2	2.4	0.049	0.055	0.085	3.9
Weed control practice						
No weeding	113	52	2.47	1.73	2.33	235
Chemical weeding	120	64	2.74	2.33	3.03	105
Beushani	114	62	2.73	2.68	3.14	43
Puddling	115	72	2.78	2.77	3.48	35
SE	1.3	2.5	0.046	0.062	0.095	3.5
N level (kg ha⁻¹)						
0	110	55	2.56	2.12	2.41	93
40	121	70	2.81	2.63	3.58	116
SE	0.9	1.8	0.033	0.044	0.067	2.4

Table 2. Interaction between tillage, weed control practice, and N level and effect on grain yield of rice (t ha⁻¹). Cuttack, India.

Treatment	Weed control practice				Mean
	No weeding	Chemical weeding	Beushani	Puddling	
Tillage					
Summer plowing	2.11	2.86	3.02	3.13	2.78
Conventional tillage	1.35	1.80	2.34	2.42	1.98
N level (kg ha⁻¹)					
0	1.55	2.02	2.43	2.50	2.12
40	1.91	2.64	2.94	3.05	2.63
Mean	1.73	2.33	2.68	2.77	
SE					
Tillage	0.055				
Weed control practice	0.062				
N level	0.044				
Tillage × weed control	0.126				
Weed control × N level	0.126				

water depth and fast canopy closure did not allow the weeds to come up. Thiobencarb did not effectively control broadleaf weeds (mainly jointvetch) and late emerging aquatic weeds. Applying 40 kg N ha⁻¹ increased plant height and number and weight of panicles and led to significantly larger grain yields, despite increased weed biomass.

Interactions between weed control practices and tillage or N levels were significant for grain yield of rice (Table 2). Inadequate land preparation under conventional tillage resulted in profuse weed growth from the early stages, which greatly reduced yield in the unweeded control and chemical weeding treatment. The differences in yield between summer plowing and conventional tillage, however, narrowed under beushani and puddling because of a considerable increase in weed biomass. Basal fertilization with N encouraged weed growth in the early stages, suppressed the growth of rice plants, and thus did not benefit the crop under the unweeded control. The increase in yield from N was significant, however, when weeds were controlled by either cultural or chemical methods. ■

Water management

On-farm water management studies in ricefields of north Bihar, India

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We studied the effects of applying improved water management technology during the wet season in canal-irrigated ricefields for 6 yr (1989-94) in the Jian minor canal of the Tirhut main canal in Gandak command, Bihar,

India. We irrigated rice to a depth of 7 cm 3 d after ponded water disappeared. This treatment was compared with the usual farmers' practice of irrigating according to the availability of water from canals and rain. Farmers generally apply more than 10 cm irrigation water continuously, especially in the head of the minor canal. Six to 18 farms were used in the study each year, with an average field size of 0.4 ha (see table). Soil was silty loam. A stage level recorder at the opening of the minor canal and Parshall flume in each outlet were used to measure irrigation water used.

In the study fields (improved practices), semitall improved rice variety Rajshree with maturity period of 145 d was tested against local photoperiod-sensitive tall aman cv Bakol (maturity 165 d) in the control (traditional practices) fields. Irrigation water varied across years depending on the amount of rain. The water use efficiency (WUE) was expressed as the ratio of grain yield to the amount of irrigation water applied. The yield and WUE of the control and study fields were statistically analyzed in a randomized block design, using number of observations as replications.

Effect of improved variety and water management practices on wet season rice crop in north Bihar, India.

Year	Total rainfall in season (cm)	Number of observations in each block	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹) in different blocks			Total irrigation on water depth (cm)		WUE ^a (t ha ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)			Saving in water consumption (cm ha ⁻¹)
			Study	Control	CD (P=0.05)	Study	Control	Study	Control	CD (P=0.05)	
1989	142.0	18	3.7	1.9	0.14	24.4	46.7	1.4	0.4	0.06	22.3
1990	91.4	9	2.8	1.9	0.51	19.3	29.9	1.4	0.6	0.07	10.6
1991	89.1	9	3.7	3.2	0.33	41.3	91.0	0.9	0.3	0.10	49.7
1992	58.4	6	2.0	1.8	0.21	31.8	44.8	0.6	0.4	0.08	13.0
1993	138.2	15	3.2	2.2	0.31	18.0	18.0	1.7	1.2	0.04	0.0
1994	96.6	9	3.1	2.4	0.33	21.0	32.0	1.0	0.6	0.05	11.0

^aWUE = water use efficiency.

The results indicated that grain yield in the study fields averaged 34% more than in the control fields. The mean depth of irrigation water ranged from 18.0 to 41.3 cm in the study fields and 18.0 to 91.0 cm in the control fields.

The WUE also differed significantly, with higher values in the study fields than in the control fields. On average, yearly water consumption was 18.1 cm more in the control fields than in the study fields.

Improved rice varieties with improved water management practices can substantially increase yield as well as WUE on farms with irrigation. ■

On-farm water management studies in summer rice

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To demonstrate the significance of improved water management practices in rice cultivation, we conducted one large-scale experiment during the 1990-93 summer (Feb-May) seasons in farmers' fields using one of the minor canals off the main canal of the Ukai-Kakrapar command area in Gujarat. The clay soil was representative of those in the area for salinity and sodicity. The infiltration rate of the soil was 2.5 mm d⁻¹.

In the study plot (SP), 5 ± 2 cm of irrigation water was applied 1 d after standing water disappeared; in the control plot (CP), farmers' practices were followed. Water depth in SP was observed using graduated, colored wooden pegs and the water application was measured using Parshall flumes installed in the canal. Water depth, measured periodically in CP, averaged 10±2 cm more across the crop growth period. No rain was received during any of the cropping seasons.

Based on the mean results (see table), 29% of the irrigation water normally used by farmers was saved, with about 55% higher yield per unit of water applied by adopting the improved water management practices. The yield increase (estimated by a

standard crop-cutting experimental technique) in SP was about 10.3% more than in CP. The increase could be attributed to the alternate wetting and drying in the treated plot, which might have resulted in better nutrient availability and less accumulation of toxic gases.

During the past 3 yr, 15% more area was brought under cultivation, especially at the end of the minor canal. Based on this research, irrigation authorities were convinced that the rice crop does not require continuous flooding at the usual higher water depths. Farmers did not experience yield reduction by using less water. Irrigating the extra 15% area used the same quantity of water normally allotted to the minor canal. ■

Response of rice to water management practices. Gujarat, India. 1990-91 and 1993.

Item	1990		1991		1993		Mean	
	SP ^a	CP ^a	SP	CP	SP	CP	SP	CP
Total rice area (ha)	34.2	10.2	28.5	9.6	25.6	11.1	29.4	10.4
Total irrigation water (mm ha ⁻¹) ^b	984	1580	1231	1762	1376	1717	1197	1686
Yield of rice (t ha ⁻¹)	5.988	6.037	6.715	6.130	7.179	5.855	6.627	6.007
WUE ^c of applied water	6.1	3.8	5.4	3.5	5.2	3.4	5.5	3.5
Water saved over control (%)	37.7		30.1		19.8		29.0	
WUE ^c improved over control (%)	57.7		56.6		52.8		55.3	

^aSP = study plot; CP = control plot. ^bIrrigation applied excluded the water requirement for raising seedling, puddling the field, and preparing the land. ^cWUE = water use efficiency.